

GENDER AND LEADERSHIP ROLES

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The social concept in the minds of people is dynamic. This dynamism has a great outcome that is observed in today's 21st century. The influential factor is the reason for this dynamism. The psyche of the people is moulded with the help of proper Education and guidance. Educating the true meaning of gender is of utmost necessity. This is often mistaken with the concept of "Ability of a men and women" . Gender is just a biological and psychological characteristics and not to discriminate by ability of the person. The issue of inequality, abuse at home or workplaces, discrimination etc. followed for millennia and is still continuing. Leadership is quality of inducing the heart mind and soul in a productive way. The topic Gender and leadership role deserves serious note as the leadership is often considered as a power of a human and not the intellectual ability. The topic must consider and discussed as it is practised in all fields like group like in Education, Organisations, Politics, Culture, Society, At home etc. A leader is the one who lead and own the value of oneness among the group no matter whether is a men or a women. The main objective of the paper is to understand the true meaning of leadership with the support of gender.

Keyword:-*Dynamism, Moulding, Education, Support, intellectual ability.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of paper contains the nature of research work, purpose of work, and the contribution of this paper.

Gender is a term where we often describe and divide in terms of status, power, strength etc. Male, Female and Transgender are the main criteria for identifying a gender. The important aspect of the research was to get the true meaning of gender in leadership roles. To become a leader is to have determination, stability and interest towards the work that is done and the work that to be get it done by others. The personality of a true leader is the passion, positivity, communication, confident, Humble etc. These qualities are either inbuilt in a human being or can be inculcated through moulding them out with the help of proper training. The concept of gender in Leadership is integrated. Leadership is incomplete until there is an application of any gender. Gender in leadership refers to male ,Female or a transgender allotted as a leader to lead a group of people in certain organisation which could either be an Institution, Political affairs, at home, in the society or in any event which has certain goals and objectives to be completed. The research work was conducted to identify the impact of gender in terms of leadership with a sample size of 75 respondents.

The purpose of conducting the research is for the urge of knowing the perception of the respondents when it comes to gender in leadership. The research plays a vital role in shaping the minds of the people, to remove the taboo of considering any gender low and unethical. To optimize leadership effectiveness of men and women, it is important to go beyond consideration of the biological sex of the individual and simplistic generalizations of what makes a male leader versus a female leader successful.

This paper will have a great impact on our society to measure their views over our research topic. Whether they are heading a major corporation or serving in elected office, leaders bring a combination of traits. The chapter is discussed with the major impact of gender in leadership role and how it is contributed in our society. The paper addresses the leadership styles and ends with the summary and a conclusion.

II. LEADERSHIP STYLES

It is rightly said that; “Leader becomes great not because of their power but, because of their ability to empower others”- John Maxwell. A leader must have the ability to shape this is done with the help of proper guidance, opportunities, and training. Following are the leadership styles for a great leader to be.

1. **Autocratic leaders** make decisions without consulting their team members, even if their input would be useful. This can be appropriate when you need to make decisions quickly, when there's no need for team input, and when team agreement isn't necessary for a successful outcome. However, this style can be disheartened, and it can lead to high levels of absenteeism and staff turnover.
2. **Democratic leaders** make the final decisions, but they include team members in the decision-making process. They encourage creativity, and people are often highly engaged in projects and decisions. As a result, team members tend to have high job satisfaction and high productivity. This is not always an effective style to use, though, when you need to make a quick decision.
3. **Laissez-faire** leaders give their team members a lot of freedom in how they do their work, and how they set their deadlines. They provide support with resources and advice if needed, but otherwise they don't get involved. This autonomy can lead to high job satisfaction, but it can be damaging if team members don't manage their time well, or if they don't have the knowledge, skills, or self motivation to do their work effectively. (Laissez-faire leadership can also occur when managers don't have control over their work and their people.)
4. **Strategic Leadership** sit at the intersection between a company's main operations and its growth opportunities. He or she accepts the burden of executive interests while ensuring that current working conditions remain stable for everyone else.
5. **Transformational Leadership** is always "transforming" and improving upon the company's conventions. Employees might have a basic set of tasks and goals that they complete every week or month, but the leader is constantly pushing them outside of their comfort zone
6. **Transactional Leadership** Transactional leaders are fairly common today. These managers reward their employees for precisely the work they do. A marketing team that receives a scheduled bonus for helping generate a certain number of leads by the end of the quarter is a common example of transactional leadership.
7. **Coach-Style Leadership** Similarly to a sports team's coach, this leader focuses on identifying and nurturing the individual strengths of each member on his or her team. They also focus on strategies that will enable their team work better together. This style offers strong similarities to strategic and democratic leadership, but puts more emphasis on the growth and success of individual employees.
8. **Bureaucratic Leadership** go by the books. This style of leadership might listen and consider the input of employees -- unlike autocratic leadership -- but the leader tends to reject an employee's input if it conflicts with company policy or past practices.

These leadership styles are followed for an effective result. When a human is given an opportunity to learn and implement these styles the problem of gender bias is just dissolved. Every human whether a male, female or a transgender must be given the chance and opportunity to grow in the society. We often take the concept wrong and lead our mind accordingly. The stereotypes should be removed

When we speak about Gender in leadership, we have great examples of a female leader Mrs. Pratibha Devisingh Patil an Indian political leader who served as the 12th President of India from 2007 to 2012. A member of the Indian National Congress, Mrs. Patil is the only woman to hold the office. Her contribution to the nation was indeed a great help. The other example in terms of politics are All India Congress president Mrs. Sonia Gandhi,

Chief Minister of Delhi from 1998 to 2013, Mrs. Sheila Dixshit, woman Chief Minister of West Bengal Mamata Banarjee, Tamil Nadu CM Jayalalitha Jayaram, etc. are the Female leaders who had contributed immensely for the nation. When it comes to Education in our Indian history we had Savitribai phule regarded as the first female teacher of India who founded the first Indian girls' school in Pune, at Bhide wada in 1848. From Arundhati Bhattacharya, Chairperson of State Bank of India, Kiran Mazumdar-Shaw, Founder of Biocon to Indra Nooyi, President of PepsiCo and Sushma Swaraj, Minister of External Affairs, the women of India have left no area untouched when it comes to holding leadership chairs. Whether it is corporate world or politics, 21st-century women can be found everywhere, displaying a statement to the world that they are second to none. Women, who are considered as born multi-tasters, never fail to bring something different to the table and groom organizations to emerge as vibrant and successful entities.

On the other hand we have men contributors in our Indian politics who has shaped our nation, freed from British slaves. Shivaji Maharaj in his ruling time is one of the great example. APJ Abdul Kalam., Rabindra Nath Tagore Dr Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan. Entrepreneur Leaders like Mukesh Ambani, Lakshmi Mittal, Dilip Shanghvi etc. Apart from these we also have Transgender in our society who has grown intellectually and emotionally strong, and become leaders in their life. We have personalities like India's very first transgender lawyer Sathyasri Sharmila, Manabi Bandopadhyay, who became India's first transgender college principal, India's first transgender judge: Joyita Mondal, India's first transgender police officer: Prithika Yashini, India's first transgender soldier: Shabi, etc.

Getting an opportunity is the most important factor for any individual to develop and to break the taboo of gender issues. In India we have seen tremendous change acknowledging leadership. Various leadership training are conducted to boost the productivity of the leaders. Focus-U is one of the great example for providing leadership training across the globe with an aim of "WE-Centric" approach. Centum Learning is another great example for process training, behavioural training, Leadership training etc.

Leadership opportunities is not only applicable at work place but also in our society, at home etc. The treatment of men and women must be equal. In a family both the men and women must have the essential rights over the household chores, participation in societal matters etc.

Objective:

The purpose of my study is as follows:

- 1) To understand equal work opportunities for men and women
- 2) To learn the presence scenario of gender bias
- 3) Equality of women and men with regard to leadership.
- 4) Equal opportunities for decision making affairs.

Hypothesis:

Following are my hypothesis for the present research

- 1) Gender discrimination is now at a least position where men and women are given equal opportunities at workplace
- 2) Leadership qualities can be enhanced with the help of proper training and opportunities.
- 3) Men and women both have the qualities that a leader should have

Sample: The sample size consisted of 75 people from different age group.

It was a descriptive type of study.

The research was conducted with help of primary as well as secondary data

Analysis

1) What is your Gender?

Graph:-

Figure:1

Discussion: According to the survey, 48% were female respondents and 52% were male respondents.

2) Your age

Graph:-

Figure:2

Discussion:- From the data collected, maximum respondents were between age group of 18-30(89.33%), and the least from age group of above 50(1.33%)..

3) Who according to you make a better leader

Graph:-

Figure:3

Discussion:- According to the survey conducted maximum number of respondents(81.33%) Replied Both men and women can make a better leader.

4) Who according to you is good at multitasking?

Graph:-

Figure:4

Discussion:- 53% of the respondents replied “Both” men and women are good at multitasking, and 40 % replied as “women” is good at multitasking.

5) Do you find gender disparities when it comes to leadership

Graph:-

Figure:5

Discussion:- 42% of the respondents agreed to the statement by saying “Sometimes” they do find gender disparities in leadership. Less number of respondents have replied to “yes”(18.67%), which states that gender disparities is decreased when it comes to leadership.

6) Following are some Leadership qualities and skills to look for in a great leader, who according to you make out the best in each cases

Graph:-

Figure:6

Discussion:- According to the survey, maximum number of respondents agreed that leadership qualities and skills like Co-operation, humility, positivity, confidence, delegation, empathy, accountability and communication, are present in both male and female.

7) An open ended question were asked i.e.

Company "X" is planning to launch a project, out of two managers with same qualification and experience, one being a female and other a male, who according to you should lead the project and why?

According to the respondents irrespective of the gender, the one with calibre and the most deserving one must be appointed as the project leader. Certain test should be conducted which will give opportunities to both male and female and accordingly the decision is to be made.

III. CONCLUSION

Once more, our endeavour has evidenced the fact that the concept of leadership is increasingly important in today's business environment. Major of our society have an open view towards gender. The stereo types on women being low and men being powerful is dissolving due to proper exposure to education, health and rights in the society. Various women related norms are implemented to enhance and up bring both the gender. It could clearly express that training programmes, development , etc must be mentored to each one in the organisation. The paper can be considered for understanding on how the youth of this 21st century think over gender in leadership.

Besides the analysis, few initiatives like Online training for women would be a great help. Work from home is of great help for women who is a sole leader of their family. Inculcating gender equality in the mind of young generations will create a huge impact in the coming generation

Thus it is concluded that Physical appearance or power is not described as a leader but acting wisely and smartly with the people for the people will lead to be successful leader.

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